

Service Delivery and Market Performance of Deposit Money Banks in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of service delivery on the market performance of Deposit Money Banks in South-West, Nigeria. A survey research design was utilized, employing a structured questionnaire on a six-point Likert scale with 67 questions to gather data. The sample comprised 395 employees from six banks: UBA, Zenith Bank, Access Bank, Polaris Bank, Wema Bank, and Jaiz Bank selected from a population of 30,352 employees. Descriptive statistics and inferential analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS were applied to test hypotheses and assess various factors. The findings show that 51% of participants agreed on reduced customer service delays, while 49.5% affirmed fast decision-making and service delivery, though a minority reported ongoing inefficiencies. The structural equation model results indicated moderate to weak relationships between Service Delivery Time (SD) and Top Management Commitment (TMC) with Customer Equity (CE), having correlation coefficients of 0.549 and 0.481, respectively. The study recommended that banks streamline service delivery processes, implement advanced management systems, and regularly review service protocols to enhance customer equity and improve efficiency.

Keywords: Customer equity, Deposit money banks, Marketing, Market performance, Service delivery

Wordcount: 172

Introduction

The increasing competition in the financial market driven by technological advancements has put pressure on banks to improve their services. However, the recent cash crunch and economic downturn have led to significant downtimes and a decline in banking service levels. Service delivery has the potential to revive comatose processes in organizations such as banks. By adopting BPR, banks can improve their service culture, train their staff more effectively, and create more opportunities for brainstorming. These changes can lead to improved performance for banks. However, the challenges faced by banks such as limited staff training, and lack of opportunities for brainstorming have led to people leaving their jobs or seeking better opportunities elsewhere. Customers' demands are also becoming more evolving as they seek flexibility and easier access to financial services. They tend to switch

banks at the slightest provocation, leading to increased competition among banks as well as mergers and takeovers within the industry.

Due to the fast-paced and ever-changing nature of the global market and the constant technological advancements, organizations must adapt and evolve their strategies and procedures to stay competitive. The Service delivery method is one such technique that can help businesses streamline their processes and improve their efficiency, enabling them to function more effectively. Management involvement has been identified as a major challenge by several scholars. This can take various forms, such as problems associated with management's active understanding and support for reengineering, or managers' failure to support the new values and beliefs required by the redesigned processes (Rahayu, 2017; Fasna & Sachie, 2019; Oyedokun, & Abubakar, 2019). Employees tend to lack new process skills and inadequate training for personnel which could be affected by the redesigned process. With the help of technology, the world has become more interconnected than ever before, and businesses are no exception. Globalization has opened new markets and opportunities for businesses to expand their reach and tap customers with diverse needs and preferences. In this highly competitive environment, it becomes imperative for businesses to stay ahead of the curve by adapting to changing customer demands and leveraging technology to enhance their offerings (Hesson, 2007).

In the contemporary banking industry, service delivery has become a critical determinant of customer satisfaction and market performance. Banks today are faced with the growing need to offer efficient, seamless, and swift services to maintain their competitive advantage and ensure customer retention. As customer expectations evolve, the ability to deliver high-quality service is essential to sustaining customer loyalty and improving financial performance. According to Zeithaml et al., (1988), service quality can be evaluated based on several dimensions, including reliability, responsiveness, and assurance, which play a vital role in customer satisfaction. The same principle applies in the banking sector, where customer satisfaction often correlates directly with service delivery efficiency, influencing overall market performance (Zeithaml et al., 1996).

The Nigerian banking sector has witnessed significant reforms and restructuring in recent decades, with increased emphasis on improving service quality and customer experience (Sanusi, 2010). Deposit Money Banks (DMBs), which constitute a substantial part of the financial sector in Nigeria, are expected to provide high-quality services while adapting to changing regulatory frameworks and technological advancements. With the adoption of innovative solutions like mobile banking, automated service delivery, and digital platforms, banks are progressively enhancing their service delivery mechanisms (Oyedokun, Arotolu, & Vincent, 2019; Pramanik et al., 2019) However, despite these advancements, challenges such as inefficiencies in decision-making, delays in service delivery, and inadequate customer care persist, adversely affecting market performance (Gimba, Vincent, & Oyedokun, 2020).

The relationship between service delivery and market performance is well-documented in the literature. Efficient service delivery can enhance customer equity, which refers to the total value a customer brings to a company over time (Rust, 2004). Studies suggest that when banks streamline their service delivery processes and reduce delays, customers are more likely to remain loyal, contributing positively to the bank's market performance (Heskett,

1994). However, when service delivery is inefficient, customers may experience frustration, leading to customer churn and, ultimately, declining market performance. Therefore, understanding how service delivery impacts market performance is crucial for Deposit Money Banks in the South-West region of Nigeria as they strive to improve their competitive standing.

Literature Review

Service Delivery

Service delivery in the banking sector encompasses a wide range of activities and processes aimed at ensuring that customers receive services efficiently and effectively. Service delivery refers to the process by which services are provided to customers or clients. It encompasses all activities involved in ensuring that a service meets the needs and expectations of its users. In various sectors, including banking, healthcare, and public services, effective service delivery is essential for maintaining customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty (Auka, 2012).

Key elements include various channels such as branch banking, online banking, mobile banking, and ATM services. Each of these channels plays a critical role in how customers access banking services. For example, branch banking offers direct human interaction and personalized advice, while online and mobile banking provide convenience and accessibility from virtually anywhere. These diverse channels cater to different customer preferences and enhance the overall service experience (Danquah, 2014).

The quality-of-service delivery is crucial in retaining customers and maintaining their satisfaction. Quality dimensions include reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. Reliable service means delivering on promises accurately, while responsiveness involves timely support and assistance. Assurance relates to the knowledge and courtesy of staff, which builds customer trust. Empathy requires understanding and addressing individual customer needs, and tangibles refer to the physical aspects of the service environment, such as the cleanliness and organization of branches and the user-friendliness of digital interfaces (Munusamy, 2010). Ensuring high-quality service across these dimensions can significantly enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Innovation plays a pivotal role in advancing service delivery in the banking sector. The adoption of digital technologies, such as AI-driven chatbots and blockchain, has revolutionized how banks interact with customers and conduct transactions (Puschmann, 2017). Self-service options empower customers to perform banking tasks independently, increasing convenience and efficiency. Additionally, integrating services across multiple channels ensures a seamless experience, allowing customers to switch between different modes of service without disruption. Measuring service delivery performance through customer satisfaction surveys, Net Promoter Scores (NPS), and Service Level Agreements (SLAs) helps banks continuously improve and adapt to changing customer expectations

(Huang & Rust, 2017). By focusing on innovation and continuous improvement, banks can better meet customer needs and stay competitive in a rapidly evolving financial landscape.

Market Performance

Market performance is the ability of the firms to meet its primary objectives. This could either be measured using financial model (sales growth or profitability) or non-financial parameters (customer satisfaction or customer loyalty). Efficiency and effectiveness are the key terms for measuring the organizational performance (Auka, 2012). Effectiveness is the achieved outcomes in relation to strategic goals/objectives and customer requirement; while efficiency connotes how economically the organization's resources are utilized by an activity such as a business process that produces a given output or delivers a given service.

Organizational effectiveness and efficiency can be measured by financial and non-financial indicators. This study considered the nonfinancial performance indicators such as customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, operational performance, speed, process improvement and service/product delivery etc (Danquah, 2014). Non-financial measures cover both the value that is delivered to the customer which may involve time, quality, performance and service, and the outcomes that arise because of this value proposition, such as customer satisfaction and market share (Danquah, 2014).

Organizational performance refers to how well an organization is doing to reach its vision, mission, and goals. Assessing organizational performance is a vital aspect of strategic management, and assessment can be through actual net results of an organization as measured against its intended goals and objectives. Organizational performance comprises of three specific areas of firm results that include financial performance and non-financial performance which are the focus of this study (Abubakar, 2016).

Organizational performance is an indicator of performance assessment achieved by the organization in a particular period (Kassahun, 2012; Oyedokun, Tade, Eso, & Abiodun-Afolabi, 2024). The evaluation of organizational performance is a measure of the effectiveness and efficiency of organizations, it is said that the organization's performance is good if the results achieved show an increase in achievement better than the previous period. In other words, how successful is the organization in achieving its objectives? The main goal of most business organizations is to reduce costs and maximize profits. Other objectives include growth, increased sales, market share, and improved productivity in terms of better quality, greater quantities of goods and services, customer satisfaction, organizational development, individual improvement (2016). It is certain that all organizations have a common goal, how to compete in the business environment and how to win competition and achieve competitive advantage. To achieve this goal, organizations are required to be flexible in responding to environmental change and developing the existing business environment through organizational transformations and to pursue a variety of approaches, including re-engineering their operations, rethinking their way of thinking, and restructuring organizational designs which has been developed in the literature of modern management,

in order to improve its performance and maintain its position in the market. Therefore, many of the modern management techniques aimed to developing activities and processes in companies are working to increase productivity, the most important method of these methods is business re-engineering (2011).

The performance of an organization can be measured in different criteria (Shaqqour& Al-Kassar, 2016). Among them is productivity, profits, growth, turnover, cost reduction, stability, cohesion, waste reduction, reducing lead times at all stages of the production process, people development, effectiveness (progress toward goal attainment), quality performance, creativity, innovation, competitiveness (competitive profile), customer satisfaction, improved employee morale and successful product/service development. BPR is often used as a multidimensional approach to measuring organizational performance, where financial, non-financial and operational measures assume equal importance. Thus, in respect of the organizational performance, the study considers multiple measurements of performance (financial performance, and non-financial performance/operational performance). The financial performance indicators consist of profit, and sales growth/revenue.

The nonfinancial indicators include operational performance, response to competition, future outlook, and success rate in new product/service launch, organizational effectiveness, customer service management, market research, customer relationship management, customer satisfaction, speed, quality service and process improvement indicators (French, 1983; Terziovski et al., 2003; Sidikat & Ayanda, 2008; Oyedokun & Oyetunji, 2022). Nevertheless, banks like every other organization try to enhance its overall performance by assessing and comparing its efficiency and effectiveness over a period of time. There are various criteria to evaluate the performance of banks for successful survival in the period of globalization and competition. Key indicators to measure organizational performance includes profitability, liquidity, management performance, leverage, market share, productivity, innovation, quality of goods and services, human resources¹. Banks are concentrating their efforts on market segments offering the potential for growth and enhancing performance, resulting in a redirection within the overall financial services sector. Innovative banking services and processes evolved as market consolidates due to mergers and acquisitions. Thus, performance enhancement efforts are aimed at a complete realignment of internal processes. In addition to cost containment strategies, the focus is now on improving customer service delivery. Organization processes must be efficient and be more customer friendly.

Theoretical Review

Theory of Constraints (TOC)

The Theory of Constraints (TOC) was developed by Eliyahu M. Goldratt in the early 1980s and is comprehensively presented in his book *The Goal*. TOC is a management philosophy that focuses on identifying and managing the most critical limiting factor (constraint) that hinders the achievement of a goal. The primary objective of TOC is to improve

organizational performance by systematically addressing and eliminating constraints. Goldratt's theory has been widely adopted in various industries due to its practical approach to problem-solving and continuous improvement. The Theory of Constraints operates on several key assumptions. Firstly, it assumes that every system, regardless of its complexity, has at least one constraint that limits its overall performance. Secondly, it assumes that improving or eliminating this constraint will lead to significant performance gains. Thirdly, TOC posits that organizations should focus their resources and efforts on managing the constraint, rather than optimizing individual components or processes in isolation. Lastly, it assumes that constraints are dynamic and can shift over time, requiring continuous monitoring and adaptation to ensure sustained improvement (Şimşit et al., 2014).

The Theory of Constraints is highly relevant to the study of Service delivery (BPR), Customer Equity, and Market Performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in South-West Nigeria. TOC provides a valuable framework for identifying and addressing the key bottlenecks that hinder the performance of DMBs. By applying TOC principles, banks can focus their efforts on the most critical constraints, leading to significant improvements in operational efficiency, service delivery, and customer satisfaction. Additionally, TOC's emphasis on continuous improvement aligns well with the objectives of BPR, enabling DMBs to achieve sustained performance gains. The theory's holistic approach also supports the integration of various factors such as top management commitment, leadership, collaborative work environment, and information technology capabilities, ensuring a comprehensive and effective strategy for enhancing market performance.

Empirical Review

This study investigated the effects of Service delivery on Organizational Productivity: The study determined the influence of customer service delivery on organizational performance of private universities in Kenya. The study was guided by the service-profit chain theory and used a descriptive cross-sectional design. The target population was 172 respondents from private universities in Kenya, with a stratified random sampling approach used to determine a sample of 124 participants. Data was collected using questionnaires, and Cronbach alpha was adopted to determine reliability. Quantitative approaches using SPSS version 23.0 generated inferential and descriptive statistical results, presented using frequency tables. The study revealed a positive and significant correlation between customer service delivery and organizational performance, proving that enhanced customer service delivery significantly improves organizational performance in private universities. The study recommended that university leadership should implement customer service delivery to achieve positive results (Kuria, 2023).

The study examined the effect of quality service capability on the performance of petroleum distributing companies in Kenya. This study involved a comprehensive survey of 32 petroleum distributing firms in Kenya, using questionnaires to gather primary data. The findings indicated that these firms widely adopted various service quality management practices. However, the study also highlighted that the biggest challenges faced in implementing these practices were the lack of visionary leadership and top management support (Munyao, 2014).

The study examined the impact of quality service capability on the organizational performance of mobile telecommunications companies in Egypt. The study used a substantial exploration instrument to survey 384 top-level and middle-level managers from three Egyptian mobile telecommunications companies. The results indicated that quality service capability positively impacts organizational performance. Additionally, the study found that these companies emphasized responsiveness, reliability, and convenience in their services to enhance organizational performance (Azza & Sally, 2018).

The study undertook a review of the airline industry in Thailand, targeting customers' perceptions of service failures, service recovery, and loyalty recovery. Using a quantitative approach, the study found a correlation between post-recovery client loyalty, customer satisfaction, and service recovery. The findings also revealed that customer service depends on service failures or the firm's profile, providing crucial insights for the airline industry and its leadership on developing key service recovery structures (Jareankiatbovorn, 2023).

The study examined the service delivery system considering factors such as employee happiness, loyalty, service quality, and competency. The study found that customer satisfaction, viewed as an intermediate variable in the service profit chain model, significantly impacts customer loyalty and organizational performance in service delivery systems. The results also showed that customer satisfaction and loyalty significantly influenced the success of Tehran Stock Exchange brokers (Fazlzadeh, 2012).

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population comprised of all customers of the six selected banks (UBA, Zenith, Access, Polaris, Wema and Jaiz bank) which is infinite and the employees of these banks extracted 30,352 from their 2023 audited financial reports. To ascertain the sample size, the study used Cochran Z-formula to arrive at 384 sample size 95% confidence level, while Taro Yamane formula was used to arrive at 395 samples for the employee respondents and was prorated to arrive at the sample size for each bank. Stratified and simple random sampling technique (mixed method) was used for the collection of data. The study utilized a well-structured questionnaire comprising 67 questions on a six-point Likert scale. Validity was ensured through content validation by senior academics and a Cronbach's Alpha test, which confirmed the reliability of the questionnaire across all variables, with values exceeding 0.7. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics (graphs, tables, etc.) and inferential analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS to test hypotheses.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of the Responses of the Customers:

Table	Category	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	1017	45.2%	45.2%	45.2%
	Female	1234	54.8%	54.8%	100.0%
	Total	2251	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Age	21-30 years	1654	73.5%	73.5%	73.5%
	31-40 years	109	4.8%	4.8%	78.3%
	41-50 years	368	16.3%	16.3%	94.7%
	Above 50 years	120	5.3%	5.3%	100.0%
	Total	2251	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Marital Status	Single	1540	68.4%	68.4%	68.4%
	Married	647	28.7%	28.7%	97.2%
	Others	64	2.8%	2.8%	100.0%
	Total	2251	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Educational Status	SSCE	240	10.7%	10.7%	10.7%
	Diploma	1272	56.5%	56.5%	67.2%
	Degree	344	15.3%	15.3%	82.5%
	Masters	363	16.1%	16.1%	98.6%
	Professional	32	1.4%	1.4%	100.0%
	Total	2251	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Most Preferred Bank	UBA	631	28.0%	28.0%	28.0%
	Zenith Bank	170	7.6%	7.6%	35.6%
	Access Bank	371	16.5%	16.5%	52.1%
	Jaiz Bank	38	1.7%	1.7%	53.8%
	Polaris Bank	63	2.8%	2.8%	56.6%
	Wema Bank	978	43.4%	43.4%	100.0%
	Total	2251	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Number of Years in the Bank	1-3 Years	817	36.3%	36.3%	36.3%
	4-6 Years	747	33.2%	33.2%	69.5%
	7-10 Years	191	8.5%	8.5%	78.0%
	Above 10 Years	496	22.0%	22.0%	100.0%
	Total	2251	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The descriptive analysis in the table provides valuable insights into the demographic and banking preferences of the survey respondents. In terms of gender, the sample was slightly skewed towards female respondents, who made up 54.8% of the total, compared to 45.2% males. Regarding age distribution, most respondents (73.5%) were between 21 and 30 years old, indicating a younger demographic. Only 4.8% were between 31 and 40 years old, while

16.3% fell between 41 and 50 years, and 5.3% were above 50 years. This highlights that most bank customers surveyed are in the early stages of their professional and financial lives. Furthermore, 68.4% of respondents were single, while 28.7% were married, and 2.8% identified as “others,” showing a predominance of single individuals in the sample.

The educational status of respondents indicates that most customers hold a diploma (56.5%), with 16.1% possessing a master's degree and 15.3% holding a bachelor's degree. This suggests that a significant portion of the respondents are well educated. Regarding bank preferences, Wema Bank was the most preferred, chosen by 43.4% of respondents, followed by UBA (28.0%) and Access Bank (16.5%). Other banks like Zenith, Polaris, and Jaiz had relatively low preferences. Finally, the tenure of customers with their banks reveals that most have been with their current bank for one to three years (36.3%), followed by four to six years (33.2%). This demonstrates a mixture of both short- and long-term banking relationships.

Responses on Service Delivery Time

SN	QUESTION	Response	Freq.	Percent	Mean	Std
1	There is a reduction in delays in serving customer	Strongly Disagree	16	4.2	4.26	1.668
		Disagree	62	16.2		
		Partially Disagree	67	17.5		
		Partially Agree	42	11.0		
		Agree	51	13.4		
		Strongly Agree	144	37.7		
2	The decision-making process for banking products/service and the period taken to deliver the product/service is fast	Strongly Disagree	-	-	4.52	1.271
		Disagree	20	5.2		
		Partially Disagree	75	19.6		
		Partially Agree	98	25.7		
		Agree	64	16.8		
		Strongly Agree	125	32.7		
3	The cycle time to serve a customer is shortened	Strongly Disagree	22	5.8	4.34	1.494
		Disagree	14	3.7		
		Partially Disagree	85	22.3		
		Partially Agree	74	19.4		
		Agree	64	16.8		
		Strongly Agree	123	32.2		

The responses of the participants on service delivery time show that about 51% of the participants agree that there is a reduction in the number of delays in service of customers in their respective banks while 11% of the participants partially agree with the statement. However, about 17.5% partially disagree with the statement. Similarly, it was observed that about 49.5% of the participants affirmed that the decision-making process for banking products/service and the period to deliver the product/service is fast though about 25.7% of the respondents partially agree with the statement. In the contrary, about 19.6% of the participants partially disagree with the statement.

Structural Equation Model

The result shows that about 49% of the participants affirmed that the cycle time to serve a customer is shortened with about 19.4% of the participants partially agree with the statement. However, 22.3% of the participants partially disagree with the statement.

In general, the responses show that majority of the participants are in support of the items used in the questionnaire with little variation in their responses.

Summary

This study explores the impact of service delivery on the Market Performance of Deposit Money Banks in South-West, Nigeria. A survey research design was employed where a structured questionnaire was used to gather data on a six-point Likert scale which comprises 40 questions to ensure accurate results. Respondents were selected from a population of 30,352 employees across six banks viz UBA, Zenith Bank, Access Bank, Polaris Bank,

Wema Bank, and Jaiz Bank resulting in a sample size of 395. The data analysis employ descriptive statistics (graphs, tables, etc.) and inferential analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS to test hypotheses and assess multiple variables for decision-making.

The findings reveal that 51% of participants agree there has been a reduction in customer service delays within their banks, with 11% partially agreeing and 17.5% partially disagreeing. Similarly, 49.5% of respondents affirm that the decision-making process and service delivery for banking products are fast, though 25.7% partially agree and 19.6% partially disagree. These results highlight a general perception of improved service efficiency, although a significant minority still experiences delays and inefficiencies in both service delivery and decision-making processes. Result from the structural equation model reveals that Service Delivery Time (SD) and Top Management Commitment (TMC) have moderate to weak relationships with CE, with correlation coefficients of 0.549 and 0.481, respectively. This indicates that these factors have some impact on customer equity. The study recommended that in order to improve customer equity, banks should streamline their service delivery processes to reduce delays and enhance efficiency. Implementing advanced service delivery management systems and regularly reviewing and refining service protocols can help ensure timely and effective customer service.

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